

The Role of Self-Doubt in Character Development of Stephanie in Andrew Knauer's *Senior Year 2022*

Kadek Olivia Novi Putriana¹, Rindrah Kartiningsih², Hariyono³

^{1,2,3}English Literature Department, Universitas Dr. Soetomo, Surabaya, Indonesia

ARTICLE INFO

Article history:

Received January 25, 2025

Revised January 30, 2025

Accepted February 15, 2025

Available online February 22, 2025

Kata Kunci:

Keraguan Diri, naskah film *Senior Year 2022*.

Keywords:

Self-Doubt, Senior Year 2022 movie script.

This is an open access article under the [CC BY-SA](https://creativecommons.org/licenses/by-sa/4.0/) license.
Copyright © 2023 by Author. Published by Yayasan Daarul Huda

ABSTRAK

Artikel ini mengkaji peran keraguan diri dalam pengembangan karakter melalui analisis terperinci tentang Stephanie Conway, karakter utama *Senior Year 2022*, yang ditulis oleh Andrew Knauer. Dengan menggunakan metode penelitian kualitatif Creswell, artikel ini menganalisis bagaimana perjalanan keraguan diri Stephanie membentuk pertumbuhan emosional dan psikologisnya. Ceritanya tentang perjalanan karakter dari masa remajanya yang berfokus pada menjadi populer dan mengalami kecelakaan yang membuatnya koma selama 20 tahun. Analisis ini menyelidiki cara-cara di mana keraguan diri memengaruhi keputusan dan interaksinya, melalui analisis naratif yang mendalam dan pemeriksaan karakter, makalah ini menyoroti bagaimana keraguan diri merupakan bagian integral dari pengembangan karakter Stephanie, yang menggambarkan perannya dalam jalan akhirnya menuju penerimaan diri.

ABSTRACT

This research aims to develop a model of Christian Religious Education that is oriented towards improving This article examines the role of self-doubt in character development through a detailed analysis of Stephanie Conway, the main character of Senior Year 2022, written by Andrew Knauer. Using Creswell's qualitative research method, this

article analyzes how Stephanie's journey of self-doubt shapes her emotional and psychological growth. The story is about the character's journey from her teenage years that focuses on becoming popular and getting into an accident that put her in a coma for 20 years. The analysis delves into the ways in which self-doubt influences her decisions and interactions, through in-depth narrative analysis and character examination, this paper highlights how self-doubt is integral to the development of Stephanie's character, illustrating its role in her eventual path to self-acceptance.

PENDAHULUAN

The idea of how self-doubt can influence a character's development is important to understand what character development and self-doubt is. Self-doubt can be defined as a state of uncertainty about the truth of one's thoughts, beliefs, emotions, and decisions (Braslow, Guerrettaz, Arkin, & Oleson, 2012). It is a powerful psychology force that influences not only individual behaviors but also shapes the narrative arcs of fictional characters. Aristotle's view of character development is a lifelong process that requires practice, rational decision-making, and a commitment to finding the balance between extremes, all of which contribute to achieving a virtuous and flourishing (Aristotle, 1999). In a movie, character development often mirrors Aristotle's ideas about the evolution of virtue, balance, and the pursuit of a meaningful life. Characters grow by overcoming flaws, making thoughtful choices, and finding balance, leading to their own version of eudaimonia, or a fulfilled life. Many movie narratives demonstrate Aristotle's theories of character development.

In movies, character's struggles with self-doubt often serve as key drivers of their development, providing both internal conflict and opportunities for growth. This article examines the role of self-doubt in the character development of Stephanie Conway of *Senior Year 2022* movie script, a comedy movie written by Andrew Knauer. A story of a teenage girl who always tries to measure up to the societal standards to be noticed by other people around her. Striving to become popular, her plan in achieving her idealized perfect life had to pause for 20 years because she was in a coma due to an accident. After waking up, Stephanie returns to high school as a 37-year-old adult, finding herself unable to reclaim the life she once envisioned for herself. Her journey is marked by a series of emotional and social challenges, all

*Corresponding author

E-mail addresses: Olivianovi75@gmail.com, Rindrah.kartiningsih@unitomo.ac.id, hariyono@unitomo.ac.id

rooted in her deep sense of self-doubt. This movie script is written by Andrew Knauer, an American screenwriter and producer, best known for his work in the comedy genre. His writing credits include the 2022 Netflix movie *Senior Year 2022*, starring Rebel Wilson, which is a comedy about a woman returning to high school after being in a coma for 20 years (Knauer 22, 2022). Knauer has also worked on other movie and television projects, often collaborating in the comedy field. Though not as widely known as some other Hollywood screenwriters, Knauer has made a mark with his writing style, contributing to the development of humorous and relatable narratives. He has worked on a variety of projects, contributing to the evolving landscape of comedy in modern movie. Specific details about his early life, education, and other works may be less documented in public sources.

The primary aim of this article is to explore how self-doubt functions as a central theme in Stephanie's character development, using Creswell's qualitative research methodology to analysis. This study will delve into how Stephanie's internal struggles with body image, social reintegration, and the fear of failure propel her emotional arc and contribute on a movie character. This article seeks to highlight the broader scope of psychological and narrative implications of self-doubt, while also examining the ways in which insecurity and vulnerability can lead to moments of resilience and self-acceptance. In focusing on the concept of how the role of character development as a virtue ethics that focuses on building inner traits and dispositions that enable individuals to flourish morally. It emphasizes the importance of becoming a virtuous person through practical wisdom, consistent habits, and the right influences, with the goal of guiding actions and decisions toward moral excellence (Bhuyan, 2007).

The researcher will use the theory of Self-Doubt by Matthew D Braslow, who was a student in Social Psychology at the Ohio State University. His research focuses on self-doubt and self-esteem, which recent work examining the role of uncertainty and threat in the phenomena of self-handicapping and overachievement. Matthew holds a BA in Psychology from Northwestern University and an MA in Social Psychology from the Ohio State University. Braslow's theory of self-doubt focuses on how individuals experience uncertainty and self-questioning. It is not inherently negative but can stimulate critical thinking and personal growth. His theory emphasizes the importance of professional development and engagement with diverse perspectives, aligning with Kenderman's view on self-doubt in educational research. Both suggest that confronting uncertainty and difference, as seen in research preparation courses, can facilitate growth and transformative learning for doctoral students (Kenderman, 2015).

In the following sections, the article will review relevant literature on self-doubt in psychology and movie script. The form of literary work can be various, one of them is movie script. The screenplay is like a movie script, both deliver the communications of ideas in narrative and dialogues (Hellerman, 2023). He specifically said, "As a written work that tells a story and communicates ideas and themes through words, a screenplay can be considered as a type of literature."

METHOD

The researcher employs a qualitative research method, following Creswell's approach, utilizing document analysis as the technique. The focus of this paper will be the movie script of *Senior Year 2022* written by Andrew Knauer. As a textual document, it offers valuable insight related to the research topic. Creswell defines qualitative research as a method for exploring the meanings individuals or groups assign to social or human issues. This process involves gathering data and analyzing data inductively from specific details to broader themes and interpreting the meaning behind the data (Creswell & Creswell, 2018). This definition underscores the exploratory and interpretive nature of the method. The researcher will conduct an observation and analyzing document of Stephanie's behavior and dialogue in the movie script to identify her Self-Doubt. Analyzing documents will include close reading and transcribing relevant dialogue and stage directions and organizing data into a form of direct quotation from the movie script, which then delivered to the readers with the analysis and conclusion underneath the quotation. The analysis will be using the theory of Self-Doubt by Braslow, Guerrettaz, Arkin, and Oleson.

THEORY

Self-Doubt

Social and Personality Compass

Braslow's theory of self-doubt revolves around the idea that self-doubt is a state of uncertainty about oneself, particularly in relation to one's abilities, decisions, or self-perception. According to Braslow, self-doubt occurs when an individual questions their competence or worth, leading to a lack of confidence in their ability to perform tasks or make decisions effectively. It involves a psychological state of insecurity and discomfort, often rising from perceived failures, external judgment, or an inability to meet personal standards. He explores the complex relationship between certainty, clarity, and self-doubt, emphasizing that while certainty and clarity are often evaluated in human social behavior, self-doubt is also an

important psychological experience. Social and personality psychologists recognize the core human motive to understand the world and oneself quickly and clearly, as it helps individuals predict and navigate daily social life. However, despite the value placed on certainty, too much certainty can be detrimental, as reflected in the works of theorists like Festinger, who caution against over confidence (Festinger, 1954).

Braslow identifies several indicators of self-doubt, primarily focusing on the internal struggles individuals face when questioning their abilities. Some of these indicators include (Braslow, Guerrettaz, Arkin, & Oleson, 2012):

1. Uncertainty about Abilities

This indicator reflects the core of self-doubt, when individuals are unsure of their capacity to meet the demands of a task or situation.

Braslow suggests that self-doubt often arises when people begin to question whether they are competent enough to succeed in the face of challenges. This lack of confidence and their skills can be paralyzed, leading them to avoid acting or attempting new tasks and the uncertainty makes it difficult for them to trust themselves, which can affect their ability to make decisions or set goals.

2. Negative Self-Evaluation

Braslow identifies that individuals experiencing self-doubt tend to have a harsh internal dialogue, constantly critiquing their own worth and abilities. This negative self-evaluation often leads to a distorted view of oneself where the person believes they are inadequate, incompetent or unworthy. This internal criticism can severely undermine one's self esteem and can result in a chronic sense of failure or incapacity, regardless of actual performance.

3. Fear of Failure

According to Braslow, the fear of failure is a powerful driver of self-doubt. When individuals select confidence in their abilities, they often become preoccupied with the possibility of failing. This fear can be paralyzing, making it difficult for them to take risks or embrace opportunities. As a result, individuals may avoid challenging situations entirely by opting instead for safer, less risky alternatives which may prevent them from realizing their potential or growing from setbacks.

4. Comparison to Others

Braslow argues that individuals struggling with self-doubt often measure their worth by comparing themselves to others. This constant social comparison can lead to feelings of inadequacy, as people with self-doubt tend to perceive others as more capable, successful, or deserving. This comparison feeds into the cycle of self-doubt reinforcing the belief that one is not enough or that they cannot compete with others even in areas where they may have strengths.

5. Avoidance in Challenges

Braslow's theory emphasizes that people with self-doubt often avoid situations that would force them to confront their insecurities. The fear of failure or being judged can lead to procrastination or withdrawal from opportunities that might require them, but overtime, this avoidance can lead to stagnation and an increased sense of doubt in their own abilities.

A study with the title *Self-Doubt and Self-Esteem: A threat from within* from Anthony D Hermann and colleagues conducted an investigation regarding the impact of activating self-doubt of self-esteem. The three-investigation resulted as a study report where it contains everyone with high enduring self-doubt, while induced with self-doubt showed no change. The findings were consistent across different experimental conditions (Hermann, Geoffrey, & Arkin, 2002). Relating these findings to Braslow's theory of self-doubt, the studies align with his perspective that self-esteem is dynamic and can fluctuate based on both enduring traits and situational factors. Braslow suggests that an individual's self-esteem is shaped by their internal self-concept, and experiences that challenge or affirm this self-concept can cause changes in self-esteem. In this case, individuals with high enduring self-doubt have a self-concept that is more vulnerable to threats to their competence such as the induction of self-doubt. This leads to a decline in their self-esteem, consistent with Braslow's theory that self-esteem can decrease when individuals perceived threats to their core self-concept. On the other hand, individuals with low self-doubt likely have a more stable sense of self, which is less influenced by the induction, supporting Braslow's idea that individuals with more secure self-concepts are less likely to experience fluctuations in self-esteem due to situational factors.

Relates to Zhao and Gong's research regarding how beliefs about ability affect self-doubt, the experiment's result leads to certain points, which are the findings of self-doubt hurt performance and increased nervousness for those with entity beliefs, but not for those with incremental beliefs. The second experiment showed that self-doubt lowered self-esteem for entity believers but had no effect on

incremental believers. However, the results were not fully consistent across experiments, indicating the need for further research (Zhao, Wichman, & Frishberg, Self-doubt effects depend on beliefs about ability: Experimental evidence., 2019).

RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

Senior Year 2022 is a movie written by Andrew Knauer and released to the public on the platform Netflix in 2022. It tells a story of a teenager with the name Stephanie Conway who is a foreigner from Australia that had just moved into the United States during her Junior High School Year, it delves into the themes of Self-Doubt regarding her uncertainty towards herself in being able to fit in with the new environment. Numerous differences between her and the societal standards pursued her to measure up in order to be accepted and feel worthy (Knauer, 2022).

Braslow's concept of Self-Doubt explains how it is a state of uncertainty regarding the truth of anything about oneself, particularly focusing on questioning one's self-competence (Braslow, Guerrettaz, Arkin, & Oleson, 2012). It involves a lack of confidence in one's ability to perform tasks or achieve goals effectively, leading to a sense of uncertainty about personal capabilities. Braslow highlights that Self-Doubt is primarily characterized by this lack of certainty in self-evaluation. The core aspect of Self-Doubt, he argues, lies in the individual's questioning of their own ability to accomplish tasks and meet goals, which ultimately undermines their belief in their competence.

The researcher will be focusing on discussing two main parts of the story. Firstly, the researcher will discuss about the situation of Stephanie's environment condition that affected the character Stephanie's behavior and development. Secondly, the researcher will focus on the discussion of numerous events that are related to Stephanie's Self-Doubt, according to the indicators from Braslow's research (Knauer, 2022). There are 5 main indicators of Self-Doubt by Braslow that were depicted by the character Stephanie. There is uncertainty about abilities, negative self-evaluation, fear of failure, comparison to others, and avoidance of challenges (Braslow, Guerrettaz, Arkin, & Oleson, 2012). These indicators will help the researcher in analyzing the supporting data that will be taking form of quotation with the simple conclusion underneath it as written below.

Data 1. *Stephanie's monologue: "When I moved to the US, I knew fitting in was gonna be hard" (Knauer, 2022)*

The opening scene where Stephanie is doing a live stream in Instagram, she mentioned her concerns about moving to a new place. Stephanie is a foreigner from Australia. Where she has different accents and traits, which makes her concerned about fitting in in a place that is strange to her.

The quotation above reflects Stephanie's Self-doubt as she anticipates difficulty in adapting to a new environment. Coming from Australia, she is aware of her differences, such as her accent and cultural traits, which make her uncertain about her ability to fit in and be accepted. This statement highlights her lack of confidence in her social competence and fear of rejection, illustrating how self-doubt can stem from external differences and affect one's sense of belonging (Zhao & Gong, Cultural differences in attitude toward and effects of self-doubt, 2019). From Braslow's perspective, Stephanie's self-doubt aligns with uncertainty about her abilities to navigate a new social environment and interact effectively with others. Her concern about fitting in and being accepted can be seen as a reflection of negative self-evaluation, where she questions her competence in adapting to the new cultural context and fears the possibility of failure in forming connections (Braslow, Guerrettaz, Arkin, & Oleson, 2012).

Data 2. *Stephanie's monologue: "I hated thinking that life wasn't for me..." (Knauer, 2022)*

In the scene where it is still during her live stream in Instagram. Stephanie mentioned hating the life of not being popular. She was very concerned about being herself that might end up making people around her hate her (Knauer, 2022).

In the above quotation, Stephanie expresses her internal struggle with self-doubt, particularly regarding her fear of not fitting into the social world she aspires to be a part of. In the context of her live stream, she reveals her deep insecurity about not being popular and the potential consequences of being true to herself. Her statement reflects negative self-evaluation, as she perceives her true identity as something that may lead to rejection or dislikes from others, showing a lack of confidence in her ability to navigate social expectations (Braslow, Guerrettaz, Arkin, & Oleson, 2012).

Stephanie's self-doubt is rooted in her fear that being authentic might prevent her from achieving the acceptance and popularity she desires. According to Braslow's definition, this moment showcases how self-doubt can stem from questioning one's social standing (Braslow, Guerrettaz, Arkin, & Oleson, 2012). Her hatred of the thought that life of popularity might not be "for her" suggests that she is unsure whether

she can succeed in the social realm, leading to a profound sense of uncertainty about her self-worth and the choices she makes.

Data 3. *Stephanie's monologue: "That I was destined to be just some average, boring, invisible girl who had no friends."* (Braslow, Guerrettaz, Arkin, & Oleson, 2012).

In the scene where Stephanie was doing a live stream in Instagram explaining about why she behaved like in the past. She mentioned average, boring, and invisible which makes her doubt herself (Knauer, 2022).

The quotation above Stephanie openly expresses the negative self-evaluation central to her self-doubt. She sees herself as unremarkable, disconnected, and lacking social worth, which reflects a deep insecurity about her identity and value in the eyes of others. Her use of words like "average", "boring", and "invisible" reveals how she perceives herself as inadequate compared to others, indicating a lack of confidence in her social and personal abilities.

Braslow stated, this is an epitomized self-doubt as it showcases Stephanie's struggle with her perceived lack of competence in forming meaningful relationships and her fear of being unnoticed or rejected (Braslow, Guerrettaz, Arkin, & Oleson, 2012). The belief that she is "destined" to be unnoticed speaks to her internalized fear of failure and reinforces the uncertainty she feels about her own potential. This sense of being "invisible" highlights her belief that she is incapable of achieving the social connections or acceptance she desires, deepening her self-doubt and sense of inadequacy.

Data 4. *[Stephanie is in the toilet waiting for Tiffany anxiously, she walks back and forth with her forehead sweating and constant sighing]* (Knauer, 2022)

In the scene where this stage direction takes place, happened in the school toilet where Stephanie is waiting anxiously for Tiffany after what she heard from Blaine about how Tiffany is planning an after-prom party, sabotaging Stephanie's plan (Knauer, 2022).

The stage direction above vividly depicts Stephanie's internal struggle and heightened self-doubt in this moment. Her anxious behavior of walking back and forth, sweating and sighing constantly, shows her deep uncertainty and fear about the upcoming confrontation with Tiffany. This anxiety reflects her lack of confidence in handling the situation effectively and her fear of failure, particularly after hearing Tiffany is sabotaging her plans (Braslow, Guerrettaz, Arkin, & Oleson, 2012).

According to Braslow, this physical manifestation of anxiety illustrates how self-doubt can cause a person to feel overwhelmed and uncertain, especially in high-pressure social situations. Stephanie's anxious waiting, coupled with the negative anticipation of the confrontation, highlights her lack of faith in this social encounter. The stage direction emphasizes her internal turmoil, revealing her deep-seated insecurity about her social standing and fear of being undermined or rejected by her peers (Braslow, Guerrettaz, Arkin, & Oleson, 2012).

Data 5. *[Stephanie to her reflection in the mirror] Stephanie: "Hello? It's very rude to be a stare bear. Hello? Are you... Stop... stop doing that! Why are you doing that, you freaky old..."* (Knauer, 2022)

When Stephanie woke up from her coma due to the cheer stunt accident 20 years ago, she woke up in a hospital room and went to the receptionist to ask what happened, without knowing that she was in a different timeline. While talking to the nurse, she glanced back to see the mirror behind her and noticed her mature figure and got confused (Knauer, 2022).

This scene highlights Stephanie's deep sense of self-doubt and confusion upon waking up from her coma. When she sees her altered reflection where her body and face appear older and her change of voice as well, Stephanie is confronted with an image of herself that does not align with her internal perception. This moment of confusion reflects her uncertainty about who she is and how she fits into the world around her.

Braslow stated, this scenario depicts self-doubt as Stephanie questions her physical and personal identity, no longer recognizing the person she sees in the mirror. The internal conflict she experiences in this scene showcases a lack of confidence in her own self-evaluation, as she struggles to reconcile the person, she wants with the person she has become. The confusion and discomfort Stephanie expresses in the moment of seeing her mature appearance illustrates the feeling of being disconnected from one's own

identity, a core aspect of self-doubt (Braslow, Guerrettaz, Arkin, & Oleson, 2012). This in reveals her fear of change and the uncertainty of how she is now perceived, intensifying her struggle with self-acceptance.

Data 6. Doctor: "You've been in a coma for almost two decades." [Stephanie staring blankly], Stephanie: "That doesn't sound right." (Knauer, 2022)

The conversation between Stephanie and her doctor took place in the room where Stephanie woke up before she passed out again after arguing with her reflections that she finds odd due to her being confused about seeing a different figure standing in front of her (Knauer, 2022).

In the scene where Stephanie replied to the doctor, after being told by the doctor that she has been in a coma for nearly two decades, her blank stare reflects a profound sense of disbelief and confusion. This moment highlights her self-doubt, as she struggles to comprehend the dramatic changes to her life and identity. Her reaction shows that she is unable to reconcile the information she's been given with her sense of reality, which indicates a lack of confidence in her understanding of yourself and her situation.

From Braslow's perspective, this illustrates self-doubt as Stephanie faces a disconnect between her internal perception and the reality presented to her. Her inability to accept the doctor's statement suggests that she is uncertain about her own identity and the passage of time (Braslow, Guerrettaz, Arkin, & Oleson, 2012). This confusion represents a key aspect of self-doubt: the questioning of one's self-perception and the fear of losing control over understanding one's place in the world. Stephanie's disbelief indicates a lack of self-assurance in navigating her changed circumstances, as she faces the daunting realization that she no longer recognizes herself in both a physical and temporal sense.

Data 7. [Stephanie examines her body in the mirror with a confused and frowned look] Stephanie: "Dad! Dad. what the F? Who was in charge of my feeding tube? My boobs are huge" (Knauer, 2022)

In the scene where Stephanie is standing in her room after being discharged from the hospital, she looks at how her body changed into a more mature body figure. She called out her dad out of confusion on what caused her body to change so much (Knauer, 2022).

Stephanie's reaction reflects a deep sense of self-doubt about her physical appearance. Stephanie's clearly startled and disturbed by how much her body has transformed during her coma, and her questioning tone reveals her answer to what has happened to her. She calls out to her dad in a frantic attempt to make sense of her altered appearance, which signifies her discomfort and confusion regarding the person she sees in the mirror.

According to Braslow, this moment embodies self-doubt as Stephanie grapples with her new, unfamiliar body. Her shock and disbelief indicate a lack of confidence in her ability to accept the changes and understand her new self. The confusion she experiences while examining her body highlights how self-doubt can manifest when someone is disconnected from their own identity both physically and emotionally (Braslow, Guerrettaz, Arkin, & Oleson, 2012). Stephanie's reaction exemplifies the insecurity and uncertainty that arise when one feels that they no longer recognize themselves reinforcing her internal struggle with self-acceptance and the fear of being out of control over her own image.

Data 8. Stephanie: "Yes, I am." (Knauer, 2022)

In the scene where it shows the flashback of Stephanie having a conversation with her mom, she put on make-up to make her look beautiful with her mother in the room and sat down next to her (Knauer, 2022).

The statement above is the moment when Stephanie was putting on makeup to look beautiful. It reveals her desire for validation and her underlying self-doubt about her appearance (Knauer, 2022). By convincing her mother that she is ugly, Stephanie expresses the need of reassurance about her self-worth, suggesting that she is uncertain about her attractiveness and identity without external confirmation. This scene reflects how self-doubt can be driven by a lack of confidence in one's appearance and the desire to align with other's expectations of beauty.

This moment highlights Stephanie's struggle with self-perception and her reliance on external validation to feel worthy (Braslow, Guerrettaz, Arkin, & Oleson, 2012). Her act of putting on makeup and seeking approval from others and not listening to her mother shows that she is unsure of her own self-competence when it comes to her physical image. This dependence on others for affirmation indicates how self-doubt can manifest in one's quest for acceptance, especially regarding aspects of identity like beauty, which can be subject to societal pressures.

Data 9. Martha: *"Oh my God, are you having a mini stroke?"* (Knauer, 2022)

In this scene, Martha (Stephanie's real friend) who also happens to be the headmaster of their Highschool, called Stephanie to her office to discuss about Stephanie's behavior. During their conversation, Martha explained how she made several changes in the school's system where she's trying to make all the students in an equal position and those changes made Stephanie shocked that she shows an absurd facial expression (Knauer, 2022).

After noticing Stephanie shocked expression, it highlights the moment of confusion and disorientation that Stephanie experiences in response to the changes Martha has made at the school system. Stephanie's facial expression and reaction signify her inability to comprehend or process these changes, which may be indicative of her self-doubt. She appears overwhelmed, as though the new developments in her environment challenged her previous understanding of the world around her, making her feel uncertain and unprepared to navigate these changes (Braslow, Guerrettaz, Arkin, & Oleson, 2012).

This scene demonstrates how self-doubt can be triggered by unexpected or overwhelming situations that shake one's sense of control and self-assurance. Stephanie shocked reaction suggests she is unsure of how to adapt to the new dynamics at school, questioning her ability to keep up or maintain her previous position. Her expression conveys the emotional and cognitive distress that accompanies self-doubt, as she struggles with feelings of being out of place or incapable of handling the alterations in her environment (Braslow, Guerrettaz, Arkin, & Oleson, 2012).

Data 10. Stephanie: *"I know I'm not. I'm an adult. Is that what you want to hear? Yes, I am a 37-year-old 12th grader. You don't think I know how crazy it is going back to high school in this body? What else was I supposed to do? What else did I have?"* (Knauer, 2022)

This scene is taking place where Stephanie and Martha had a heated argument after the after-prom party that Stephanie held in Martha's Lake house got reported to the police by Tiffany. The argument between them became intense and it made Stephanie express her doubt in herself about moving on after sleeping for 20 years (Knauer, 2022).

The quotation above reveals the deep self-doubt Stephanie feels about her situation and the identity crisis she is experiencing. Her tone is miserable, underscoring the emotional weight of the conflict she is facing. Stephanie's admission highlights her internal struggle as she recognizes the absurdity of her situation but feels trapped, unable to reconcile her present self with her past (Braslow, Guerrettaz, Arkin, & Oleson, 2012).

This moment exemplifies self-doubt in its most raw form. Stephanie's disbelief about returning to high school as a 37-year-old reflects her uncertainty about how to navigate this surreal new reality, which challenges her sense of self and her place in the world. She's questioning her ability to adapt and move forward, overwhelmed by the dissonance between her current identity and the expectations placed on her. Her self-doubt is also evident in the way she expresses frustration and resignation, as if she feels that her option has been limited by the strange circumstances of her life. This encapsulates how self-doubt can arise from an individual's struggle to accept significant changes in their life and the uncertainty about how to rebuild one's sense of purpose and identity.

ANALYSIS

Senior Year 2022 is a comedy movie about a woman named Stephanie Conway (played by Rebel Wilson), who at 17, is a popular high school cheerleader and on the verge of becoming prom queen. After a traumatic accident that leaves her in a coma for 20 years, she wakes up in her 30s with no memory of the time that passed. When she returns to high school to finish her senior year, she struggles to fit into the world that has changed while she was unconscious. Stephanie decides to reclaim her former popularity and pursue her dream of becoming prom queen, all while navigating modern-day, high school dynamics, rekindling relationships with old friends, and facing the fact that life, priorities, and even her own identity have drastically changed in her absence. The movie is a blend of humor learn as Stephanie learns to reconcile her past with the present. By the conclusion of the movie above shows how the role of Self-Doubt influenced Stephanie's character development. It also explains how and why the character's Self-Doubt influenced her life in decision-making, behavior, and attitude throughout the story. Stephanie's journey in achieving her idealized life of being perfect is covered by her self-doubt. A teenage version of Stephanie conducts several actions in order to measure up to societal standards. Her actions that delve into the rotation of low self-esteem and filled with uncertainty often drive her to doubt herself.

In *Senior Year 2022*, Stephanie's journey clearly reflects Braslow's theory of self-doubt, particularly in how her self-doubt manifests through uncertainty about her abilities, negative self-evaluation, fear of failure, comparison to others, and avoidance of challenges. Stephanie's self-doubt arises when she questions her ability to fit into a new social environment. Her concerns about her accent, cultural differences, and the potential for rejection showcase her uncertainty about her social competence and how well she can navigate her new surroundings. Braslow's theory suggests that this lack of confidence in her ability to adapt and form connections paralyzes her, preventing her from fully engaging with the new opportunities around her. The fear of failure is central here, as Stephanie's concern that she will fail to meet the expectations of others leads to hesitation and a sense of being out of place.

Stephanie's internal struggle with self-acceptance and her reliance on external validation throughout the movie align with Braslow's concept of negative self-evaluation. When Stephanie looks in the mirror and is confronted with her physical transformation after waking from her coma, she struggles to reconcile her past self with her new reality. This external change leads to internal confusion and insecurity about her identity, as she feels disconnected from her self-image. Her negative self-evaluation extends to her appearance, as she questions her attractiveness and seeks reassurance from others. This harsh internal dialogue distorts her self-perception, reinforcing her feelings of inadequacy and further deepening her self-doubt.

As Stephanie navigates high school and the complexities of her new life, her fear of failure is exacerbated by her tendency to compare herself to others. She believes that she is destined to be "invisible" and struggles to keep up with her peers, reinforcing her belief that she is not capable or deserving of social success. Braslow's theory highlights how such comparisons can contribute to a cycle of self-doubt, as individuals perceive others as more competent or deserving, which in turn deepens their own feelings of inadequacy. Stephanie's fear of failure and avoidance of challenges in this context aligns with Braslow's notion that individuals with self-doubt often choose safer, less risky options to avoid confronting their insecurities.

Throughout the movie, Stephanie often avoids confronting her insecurities, such as when she struggles to embrace her new identity or when faced with potential rejection from her peers. Braslow notes that avoidance is a common coping mechanism for those with self-doubt, as it allows individuals to sidestep situations that might highlight their perceived inadequacies. Stephanie's reluctance to fully accept her new reality, such as returning to high school after her coma, demonstrates how avoidance can lead to stagnation and a deeper sense of doubt in one's abilities.

The study by Hermann et al. (2002) aligns with Braslow's theory by demonstrating that individuals with high enduring self-doubt experience a decline in self-esteem when induced with self-doubt, whereas those with low self-doubt show no change. This finding reflects Braslow's assertion that self-esteem is dynamic and influenced by both internal self-concept and external challenges. For Stephanie, her enduring self-doubt makes her self-esteem highly vulnerable to situational threats, such as the challenges of adapting to her new identity and social environment. This dynamic vulnerability is consistent with Braslow's argument that individuals with a more secure self-concept (lower self-doubt) experience fewer fluctuations in self-esteem, while those with high self-doubt face greater emotional and cognitive distress when their abilities or identity are questioned.

CONCLUSION

Regarding the analysis above, the researcher concludes that Stephanie Conway's journey clearly illustrates Braslow's theory of self-doubt, as her internal struggles with self-esteem and identity are central to her character development. From her concerns about fitting into a new social environment to her reliance on external validation, Stephanie's self-doubt is shaped by uncertainty, negative self-evaluation, fear of failure, comparison to others, and avoidance of challenges. These elements drive her behaviour throughout the movie, leading to moments of confusion and insecurity as she attempts to reconcile her past and present. As she grapples with physical and identity changes after waking from a coma, her negative self-evaluation deepens, manifesting in her self-consciousness about her appearance and her feeling of being out of place in the world around her. These aspects align with Braslow's theory, which suggests that excessive self-doubt results in a distorted self-concept, a constant need for reassurance, and avoidance of situations that might highlight perceived inadequacies.

The analysis of Stephanie's character in relation to Braslow's theory of self-doubt demonstrates that the movie effectively portrays how self-doubt shapes her emotional and cognitive experiences. The dynamics of her self-esteem, influenced by both enduring self-doubt and external factors like social comparisons and the fear of failure, reinforce her feelings of inadequacy and insecurity. Stephanie's reluctance to confront her insecurities and her avoidance of challenges further highlights the cycle of self-doubt that keeps her from fully embracing her new reality. This dynamic vulnerability is consistent with

Braslow's assertion that individuals with high self-doubt experience fluctuations in their self-esteem and cognitive distress. Ultimately, *Senior Year* portrays how self-doubt impacts Stephanie's journey, showing how it shapes her decisions, interactions, and sense of self, reinforcing the broader implications of Braslow's theory.

REFERENCES

- Aristotle. (1999). *Nicomachean ethics*. (T. I. Trans., Trans.) Hackett Publishing.
- Bhuyan, N. (2007). The role of character in ethical decision-making. *J. Value Inquiry* 41, 45.
- Braslow, M. D., Guerrettaz, J., Arkin, R. M., & Oleson, K. C. (2012). Self-Doubt. *Social and Personality Psychology Compass* 6, 470-482.
- Creswell, J. W., & Creswell, J. D. (2018). *Research Design Qualitative, Quantitative, and Mixed Method Approaches*. Los Angeles: SAGE.
- Festinger, L. (1954). A theory of social comparison. *Human relations* 7(2), 117-140.
- Hellerman, J. (2023, December 05). *How to Write a TV Show Pilot (Drama or Sitcom)*. Retrieved from nofilmschool: <https://nofilmschool.com/write-a-tv-show>
- Hermann, A. D., Geoffrey, L. J., & Arkin, R. M. (2002). Self-doubt and self-esteem: A threat from within. *Personality and Social Psychology Bulletin* 28 (3), 395-408.
- Kenderman, D. (2015). Preparing educational researchers: The role of self-doubt. *Educational Theory* 65 (6), 719-738.
- Knauer 22, A. (2022). *Senior Year 2022*. United States: Netflix.
- Knauer, A. (2022). *Senior Year (2022 Movie Script)*. Retrieved from SubsLikeScript: https://subslikescript.com/movie/Senior_Year-5315212
- Zhao, Q., & Gong, L. (2019). Cultural differences in attitude toward and effects of self-doubt. *International Journal of Psychology* 54 (6), 750-7758.
- Zhao, Q., Wichman, A., & Frishberg, E. (2019). Self-doubt effects depend on beliefs about ability: Experimental evidence. *The Journal of General Psychology* 146(3), 299-324.